

IMPLEMENTATION OF TIKTOK POPULAR CULTURE AS A DIGITAL MARKETING TECHNIQUE TO ATTRACT CONSUMERS

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Abstract

Children today must be very familiar with the Tiktok application. Tiktok has developed as a popular culture among the public by utilizing the sophistication of mass-copying technology with the aim of making it faster and easier to reach by the public without any limitations of space and time. Tiktok As one of the popular culture is entertainment and is a product that is traded for material interests in the purpose of seeking profit. One of the uses of tiktok is for digital marketing. Digital marketing is the application of digital technology to create channels that can connect with potential consumers so that the goals of business actors can run effectively. The purpose of this research is to find out Tiktok Culture as a Digital Marketing Technique to Attract Consumers. The research method used is qualitative using descriptive analysis techniques. The results show that the development of social media has a very large impact on the development of popular culture such as the TikTok application because with this application there is an introduction and cultural exchange involving advances in information technology. In the TikTok Application there is a cultural distribution of a mass information system aimed at a wide audience which is run based on a new media system. Besides the place where distribution and cultural exchange occur, the TikTok application is also used as a digital marketing tool where the features in the TikTok application such as hashtags, videos, music, stickers, etc., are proven to increase sales of marketed products.

Keywords: Culture, Tiktok, Marketing Strategy, Digital Marketing, Consumer, Features.

A. INTRODUCTION

Who are young people today who don't know the TikTok application, almost all countries know the application that is booming among young people. The hype phenomenon from TikTok users certainly affects the existing socio-cultural life (Craig et al, 2021). Especially during the current covid 19 pandemic, everyone is expected to stay at home, of course there will be boredom, tiredness, and stress. For some Tiktok people is a boredom busting application (Zuli & Zuli, 2020).

According to a survey from Sensor Tower quoted from Okezone.com, the TikTok application has now defeated other large applications such as Instagram, Facebook (Ferdiansyah, 2020). Currently, TikTok is included in the context of popular culture, because at this time TikTok has become a new trend among Indonesian people. If we look at FYP TikTok there are lots of people from outside the region who have different cultures for each person, from here we can see what the habits of the people there are like. The breadth of community groups in Indonesia today can be reached such as: ethnicity, religion, tradition, culture, social class and so on (Kusumawardhani & Sari, 2021).

TikTok is an audio-visual social media where people can see visuals (images) and audio (sound). Usually, the TikTok application is used to create short videos and contains interesting features such as filters, music, and so on (Hurley, 2022). In the TikTok application we can find

out all the information that is currently phenomenal quickly and easily, usually this information is presented in an interesting and creative form by content creators so that the audience does not feel bored (Schellewald, 2021). The TikTok application is also liked by the public because the features available are very interesting such as effects, music and examples of movement from music (Shutsko, 2020).

The presence of the TikTok application, which is currently being hype, has had a considerable influence on the socio-cultural conditions of the community. Initially, the TikTok application was known for uploading videos that were just for fun or entertainment (Kurniawan, 2022). Now, the TikTok application can be used as a place to learn or educate, now we can see that at FYP there are already a lot of content creators who make educational videos such as introducing a region's culture, regional make-up tutorials, dancing regional dances and many others. That way later on, the audience who still doesn't know the culture of an area after seeing these educational videos, the public will understand (Damayanti & Gemiharto, 2019).

However, the use of TikTok also has a negative impact on content creators, such as teenagers who now like to sway happily in front of the camera. Rocking fun here is done too vulgarly by teenagers and children because they use too minimal clothes to use and the movements are too vulgar (Damayanti & Gemiharto, 2019). This is done solely to increase TikTok's FYP. Another negative impact of TikTok is that from the TikTok application itself, there are currently a lot of videos that are inappropriate for showing and provide bad examples for viewers because they contain racist values. Some examples include the TikTok application as a trigger for comparisons of content that shows social and economic life which makes TikTok a medium to exist and shows differences in status in society, which can cause social jealousy (Pratiwi & Husen, 2021).

The tiktok application is not only to relieve boredom, some people also interpret the tiktok application as a money-making application. The Tiktok application at this time is often used as digital marketing (Guarda et al, 2021). For example, such as the promotion of a new product, make-up products, promotions for hangouts or cafes and others. People use the tiktok application to promote their wares by doing live streaming, dancing while promoting goods, lots of discounts and free shipping to make people interested (Rowles, 2022).

The internet has entered the business world which has then made a new shift, one of which is in terms of marketing strategy (Vaccaro & Cohn, 2004). One can now create a new marketing strategy with digital content in promoting its products to consumers by spreading it on social media (Tsimonis & Dimitriadis, 2014). Given that now there are so many social media users. The emergence of the internet has indeed brought a considerable influence in the business world, especially in marketing that is carried out on social media. Online marketing is what is then called digital marketing. Digital marketing is the use of technology to assist marketing activities that aim to provide information to consumers by adapting to their needs (Chaffey & Ellis_Chadwick, 2019). Indeed, currently there are many business people who are doing digital marketing to market and promote their products.

The purpose of digital marketing or digital marketing itself is to connect consumers and companies who can share information and communicate (Coviello et al., 2001). This digital marketing activity has indeed become a separate trend in this day and age. Based on research from Constantinides (2014), digital marketing has several techniques and practices of its own, ranging from SMS, banners, and other media. As we know from the beginning when marketing first entered the realm of mobile phones, these messages were messages sent in the form of text that were sent en masse to several other mobile phone users. All things marketed are messages in the form of text so that to know what is contained in the message, consumers must read it first. Then after that, promotional advertisements began to appear which distributed using banners were, the beginning of the advertisements delivered using banners were also advertisements in text form (Webber, 2013).

The development of technology is also the driving force for the shift in the marketing system from conventional models to digital where digital media consists of text, sound, images and videos that utilize computer or laptop technology and also cellphones (Hasibuan et al, 2020). Turning to the internet, digital marketing has begun to adopt everything in multimedia such as text, sound, images and video into a useful unit to attract customers to what is offered by sellers, this is what makes digital marketing more popular, and coupled with the existence of media social media that can be used for free and can also be downloaded easily, which makes it a factor for sellers to take advantage of this as a first step for marketing (Tresnawati & Prasetyo, 2018).

From the description of the phenomena and theories that have been explained, there are problems that explain the Tik Tok application as a popular culture that can not only be used as a place to socialize and interact on social media but can also be used as a marketing tool by utilizing the existing technology in the Tiktok application.

B. METHOD

The method that will be used in this research is qualitative. According to Kirk et al (1986) qualitative methodology is a particular tradition in social science that is fundamentally dependent on human observations and relates to these people in their discussion and terminology. In general, the notion of qualitative research is a multiple-focused method that involves an interpretive and mandatory approach to each subject matter. According to Denzin, qualitative research involves researchers actively in collecting empirical data through various ways and methods, one of which is using Content Analysis. Content analysis is an alternative method to the deadlocks of text analysis in the media, which has been dominated by content analysis with positivist and constructivist paradigms. This research uses triangulation technique for data validation. Triangulation is a technique used to check the validity of data that utilizes something outside the data to check and as a comparison against the data (Moloeng, 2010). Researchers use research triangulation, which involves researchers from different disciplines in the same research. This research triangulation technique is also later expected to gain knowledge of the information sought from research subjects.

C. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Role of Social Media in Shaping TikTok's Popular Culture

Developments that occur in the world of social media make a person compelled to show himself on social media in order to be the center of attention. With developments in social media, the number of individuals who use social media is increasing as well (Ohiagu & Oktorie, 2014). One of the social media applications that is currently on the rise is Instagram because Instagram can share stories that are not only in the form of writing but also support sharing stories in the form of images and videos so as to increase individuals who are interested in exposing their daily activities. Almost every day there will always be posts from students who post their activities outside, especially those who are hanging out in cafes or famous places and this is usually referred to as hedonism. However, the existence of social media is not only a bad influence, but there is also a good influence. One of the good effects is that with the existence of social media, many communities are formed in which individuals who rarely show what they have (Dittmer & Bos, 2019). The influence of social media on lifestyle can come from various sources, one of which is from role models who currently have an impact on their followers. This is something that is being encountered a lot because the more famous a person is, the higher the impact on his followers. It could be a good thing or a bad thing depending on the personal perspective of each (Burgess & Gold, 2015).

According to Kaplan & Haenlein (2010) social media is a group of internet-based applications built on web ideologies and technologies that lead to the occurrence and exchange of user-generated content. In its development, social media can be used for various purposes, ranging from making friends, certain campaign programs (educational, social, religious), environmental, health, and so on), to the promotion and marketing of certain products or services. Technological progress has been very rapid. This progress brings positive aspects in several ways, such as the many viral videos that introduce various languages in Indonesia. Social media has had a big impact on people's lives in all aspects, such as in political, social, economic and cultural aspects. In addition, using social media also has several positive and negative effects that do little to touch people's lives (Subrahmanyam et al, 2008).

A social media also makes it easier for someone to be very creative because at this time there are many ways how we give our knowledge to our audience on social media, for example by making vlogs or video blogs where we tell stories not only using words as is generally done in a social media. Blog, but by using videos that tell stories about what we experience or what we do. There are several types of vlogs, namely daily, travel, food, gaming, beauty, review and unboxing, and each type of vlog has different audiences. This is one way how we can become productive people in a very easy way as long as we have high determination and intention (Rajaram & Machanda, 2020). Almost all of the existing vloggers are young people born in the millennial era. They already understand and have understood how the current world of social media works, such as who the target is, how to do it and what are the plans for the future. They learn from people who also make vlogs so they can be productive like their role models.

Media "Tik Tok" is a new media (new media) that is popular among people all over the world. New media is anything that can flow information from information sources to recipients of information that can create innovations, or changes that can produce something that people really want (Surahman, 2018). New Media is a communication medium, which includes both material and cultural products from a mass information distribution system aimed at a wide audience and based on a modern marketing system. "New Media" is divided into several types (1). Interpersonal communication media, (2). Interactive game media, (3). Information search media, (4). Collective media for participation (Lister et al, 2009).

In this case the most popular and influential social media is the social media "Tik Tok". Xu et al (2019) explain "Tik Tok" is a Chinese social network and music video platform launched in September 2016 by Zhang Yiming, the founder of Toutiao. This app allows users to create their own short music videos. The "Tik Tok" application is known and was first launched in September 2016. At that time, this application was immediately accepted in Indonesia. "Tik Tok" app was developed by Beijing ByteDance Technology and originated in China. Can be downloaded via the Play Store for Android users and the Apps Store for iOS users. You can also open it via PC. However, at that time, many people called "Tik Tok" users as alayers when viewed from a negative perspective. The habit of "Tik Tok" users is to make videos that have been played by the first user in a theme, then the next user imitates the viral videos. One example is a video about the mention of Indonesian regional languages. It started with a video mentioning the regional language that went viral, then many videos popping up mentioning various Indonesian languages were scattered. This certainly has a positive impact on the existence and popularity of the variety of Indonesian. Many users, even just tiktok video listeners ranging from children to adults, know the language of one of the regions of Indonesia.

The Tik Tok application is a social media application that is currently on the rise, almost all of the users of this application are Instagram application users as well. Tik Tok is an application to create and publish a video that is approximately 30 seconds long. This application is a very popular social media application because Tik Tok has very diverse effects, from inserting songs, adding filters, editing videos so that it encourages users to be more creative in publishing their videos. One of the things that stands out in Tik Tok is that this application is used by many people to show their existence in their social circle. Existence is an effort to find and understand his personality which has an impact on his surroundings and himself, if an individual is considered to exist then he can get along and compete with the people around him which ultimately leads to a narcissistic personality where someone will always want to show himself that he is someone who can be imitated by others because they feel they are the best from around them (Herman, 2019).

Research conducted by Batoebara (2020), explains whether the social media application Tik-Tok is an application that is used with the aim of having fun or making its content stupid. Users of the Tik-Tok social media application are not only teenagers, there are also users from among children and adults. So basically a lot of things happen that can be said to be outside the ethics of a human being where young people insult adults indirectly and adults respond to them too, so there is a lot of chaos on social media. One of them is by doing cyber bullying, conducting

private chats by sending indecent photos. Even so, the development of this social media application has increased to become one of the rising social media applications and has quite a lot of users. Tik-Tok provides various effects and various features so that users don't feel bored. In addition, the Tik-Tok application has received support from various singers around the world so that all videos made can be inserted whatever song the user wants. Tik-Tok is a social media application that is not only famous in Indonesia but is already worldwide. Videos made by Tik-Tok users can indeed be said to be videos that can make us laugh, but indirectly they provide videos that make them look stupid. What is done is an activity that is stupid, such as accidentally falling after jumping, then getting out of a moving car, hitting a pole, and much more.

Digital Marketing Strategy Using the Tiktok Application

The presence of TikTok is considered to have contributed to advancing the business. Through the TikTok application, many users are promoting their business, from MSMEs to big brands such as Guess, Prada, Samsung, and so on. This is what is known as TikTok Marketing. TikTok marketing or TikTok digital marketing is a marketing technique carried out by a brand on TikTok social media. Digital marketing TikTok is a digital marketing method that provides useful facilities for business activists. With all the existing features and facilities, TikTok provides a variety of statistical insights and advanced tools that can be used by business people such as TikTok for Business which is useful in providing businesses with a comprehensive audience engagement analysis.

In order to be more optimal in the digital marketing strategy, it is necessary to know what features exist in the Tiktok application that can support it:

1. Added music

TikTok is a music video platform. This means, one of the main features of the TikTok application is the addition of music. Here we can add various types of music according to the video content that we want to make. In addition, we don't have to worry about using the music freely, because all the music that is already available in the application, has received permission from the owner, so it will not be subject to copyright.

2. Filters on videos

The second feature that all TikTok users can use is the filter feature in the video. Users can add filters to the video to change the color tone of the video. In addition, users can adjust the tone and hue according to the video object.

3. Sticker filters and video effects

TikTok provides at least 5 categories of effects that we can try, including visual effects, sticker effects, transition effects, split effects, and time. In sticker effects, users can find various options such as, hot, classic, selfie, hair, funny, interactive, heart, vlog, animal and glasses. This filter aims to make the videos that are made seem more creative

4. Voice Changer Filters

As users, we can now change the sound in the videos we create by using this Voice Changer feature. With a variety of different sound effects, you can now add fun and creativity to their videos with ease. The method is also quite easy to do, we only need to record or can choose from our smartphone gallery, then select the voice effect.

5. Beautify Filters

For those of us who want to appear more confident in every video we make, TikTok provides a beautify feature that can make users' faces look much prettier or more handsome, even cooler and unique. In addition, this feature can also adjust the shape of the face, eye color, and also refine the face.

6. Filter auto captions

This feature is one of the new features provided by TikTok. This feature allows Tik Tok content creators to include subtitles that are automatically generated by the app. The purpose of providing this feature is to make it easier for everyone so that they can easily access or enjoy the videos created, especially for those who have difficulty hearing. How to use it is also easy, we only need to click the "Caption" feature on the editing page before uploading the video. After that, the words spoken by the creator in the content will be automatically transcribed by the app. After that, we can see and edit the subtitles that have been made so that the text is not wrong.

7. Features Delete comments and block users en masse

TikTok is also introducing a new feature that can make it easier for creators to ward off bullying. Unfortunately, not all parties support the launch of this new feature. The reason is, many think that using this new feature allows creators to change their personas, where their uploaded content looks well received. Even though there may be a lot of TikTok audiences who reject it. To use it, users can long press on a comment or tap on the pencil icon in the upper left corner to open options. From there, creators can choose 100 comments or accounts to delete or block instead of having to go through each one individually. That way deleting comments or blocking accounts can be easier.

8. Live Features

TikTok also has a live feature that users can use. Unfortunately, unlike other social media platforms, not all TikTok users are allowed to start live videos on the platform. The reason is that only users who have a minimum of 1000 followers can do live on TikTok.

9. Use hashtags in making videos

Hashtags are part of the information in the video. Hashtags are important because they can be used as a reference for providing video recommendations to other TikTok users. But what users need to know is that using hashtags also has a technique, you know. Use the hashtags that are most relevant to your content and business.

10. Create Hashtag Challenge

If in the previous point we included hashtags in our video information, then here, Friends of Entrepreneurship can create an interesting challenge, so that other TikTok users can participate.

11. Collaborate with key opinion leaders

From the research results, 86 percent of marketers entrust key opinion leaders or influencers to increase brand awareness and product sales. The most important thing in this case is to adjust the influencer to our target market. What's interesting, influencers here are not only about artists or public figures with fantastic costs, but we can also collaborate starting from micro influencers. Again, the most important thing is to make sure the person we collaborate with is in accordance with the target market of our product.

12. TikTok Ads

Like other social media platforms, TikTok also provides paid advertising services. There are four types of advertising products offered on TikTok, including: InFeed Ads: ads appear when users scroll through feeds

- Promotes Hashtag Challenge: ads that invite users to use the hashtag challenge
- Branded Effects/Filters: filters or special effects that contain product information
- Brand Takeover: exclusive advertisements in the form of images, gifs, or videos that only appear once a day when you first open the application

In order for the content of our creation to be liked by people so as to make sales of our products increase, there are several steps that can be taken, including:

a. Using the appropriate hashtags

Several brands or online entrepreneurs are known to have done quite a lot of marketing strategies through TikTok because the fact is that it can indeed bring many benefits. The reach of TikTok users is very wide, ranging from children, teenagers, parents, even middle-aged people, all of whom are interested in watching TikTok as a refreshing entertainment. Therefore, TikTok has become a social media that has great potential as an online promotion media. Now it's just a matter of how you apply the right digital marketing strategy so that you can reach these TikTok users. One of the marketing strategies through TikTok that is worth trying is using hashtags. Hashtags are markers for a particular topic so that they are easy to find, usually by including a hashtag (#). This means that when you search for a topic, name, event, even product, using a particular hashtag, you will find it easy. TikTok's video content relies heavily on hashtags. When you select the discover menu, the videos that appear are sorted by hashtag and popularity. In order for the videos you make to appear, then choose a hashtag that is more specific and can become your TikTok trademark.

b. Follow trends and create interesting content

TikTok marketing methods focus on films that feature a variety of topics that are popular and of interest to a large number of people. With the purpose of satisfying many people's need for an entertainment video, you must consider and create what kind of engaging material to include in your TikTok films. Just bear in mind that TikTok trends change quickly. So, if you come across a moment that corresponds to the product or service you want to market, or when you want to present your firm, generate content right away. If the trend passes, you must keep an eye out for the next one to ensure that the marketing you undertake is on track.

c. Collaborating with TikTok influencers

TikTok marketing tactics may reach a larger market and gain more viewers. You may also partner with TikTok influencers to reach this larger market. To cooperate, you must first identify which influencers are popular and have a huge following. The second thing to consider is the kind of influencers with whom you wish to collaborate. To begin, do a study of the influencer's target audience. Whether or whether their audience is similar to your target market. Collaboration is possible if it is suitable. Remember to utilize the Duet with Me function to make cooperation more engaging.

d. Make a clear description

Someone will be interested to see the video or content created if there is a clear description. Descriptions combined with hashtags are a marketing strategy through TikTok that can be considered effective. Because hashtags can bring in more viewers, while descriptions will make someone better understand the content created. In addition to making clear descriptions, you can take advantage of various effects available on TikTok to make videos more unique and interesting, such as trending effects, new interactive, funny, world, and so on. You can also use the green screen effect which lets you change the background of the video.

e. Post videos often and occasionally advertise

The last thing that needs to be done is to regularly post TikTok videos. The number of videos uploaded will certainly make more people visit your account. Visitors often see many movies at once rather than just one. As a result, the more videos you publish, the more chances they will have to view them. If your TikTok channel has a lot of traffic, there's nothing wrong with periodically posting an ad on TikTok as a call to action and meeting your targeted social media and digital marketing objectives.

D. CONCLUSION

Social media has had a considerable impact on the development of popular culture around the world. With social media as part of the development of pop culture, social media has become a means of seeding ideas, self-expression, and being part of the commodification of messages. Popular culture as represented in social media characterizes the existence of a fluid (easily changing) cultural tendency. One of the popular cultures is the TikTok application. This application is a very popular social media application because Tik Tok has very diverse effects,

from inserting songs, adding filters, editing videos so that it encourages users to be more creative in publishing their videos. Through this Tiktok application, cultural and surface exchanges occur for the Indonesian people, especially those who do business using social media to reach those who are far from the location of business actors selling their products or services. Social Media besides acting as a place to introduce culture also acts as an effective marketing medium. Especially with the rise of social media such as Tiktok, it makes it easier for business actors to be able to offer their services and products to various regions. With tiktok as a marketing medium or digital marketing, of course, it makes it easier for marketers to offer what we sell to various people around the world, and of course it is useful for readers to know how important the rising social media tiktok is to their business. . The author hopes that in future research, it will be examined further how the development of the world of social media, especially tiktok as a marketing media or digital marketing.

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